

FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF CHICKENPOX IN UNVACCINATED CHILDREN AND THE NEED FOR VACCINATION

**Makhmudov I.,
Novruzova G.**

Azerbaijan Medical University I Department of Children's Diseases
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226798>

Abstract

In the presented study, the results of observations of 22 children with chickenpox over the past 5 years were interpreted. It was found that children 1-3 years old (72.7%) predominate among those with chickenpox. The clinical picture of chickenpox in children proceeds in a typical form with intoxication, catarrhal syndrome and the development of exanthemata. However, in children who have not received the vaccine, especially those suffering from immunodeficiency, the disease can become severe and often accompanied by the development of complications.

Keywords: chickenpox, children, infection, complications, vaccinoprophylaxis

Chickenpox (Ch) disease, which is related to children's droplet infections and is usually accompanied by general intoxication symptoms and characteristic vesiculous rashes, is a highly contagious infection and is registered mostly in preschool and school-aged children and can cause large outbreaks every 2-5 years. Although the first information about chickenpox disease was interpreted by the Italian anatomist and doctor G. Vidius in the middle of the XVI century, the name varicella was given by the German doctor O. Vogel (1772), who distinguished it from the natural smallpox (variola). After the epidemic of 1868-1874, in other words, since 1911, smallpox disease was registered as a separate nosological unit by the Brazilian doctor E. Aragao. The causative agent of chickenpox is considered to be Herpes zoster DNA-containing type III herpes strike belonging to the *Herpesviridae* family. On the 3rd-4th day of the disease, the amount of viruses that accumulate in large numbers in chickenpox blisters gradually decreases, which means after the 7th day. In countries with a temperate climate, infection occurs mainly at a young age (>90% in countries that have not joined the vaccination program), and in tropical countries-at an older age. According to some reports, in the last decade, the incidence of chickenpox, which ranks 2nd after acute respiratory infections (ARI) among airborne infections, has increased by about 2.2 times, of which 93.7% fall on children [1-2]. The indicator of incidence of chickenpox continues to remain at a high level today due to the lack of mass active immunization among the population. Diagnosis is based, as a rule, on clinical signs. After contact with the causative agent, immunoglobulin (VariZIG) can be injected into the muscle for the purpose of preventing the development of infection or weakening its course. In this case, it should be borne in mind that the introduction of immunoglobulin as early as possible (within 10 days after contact) can change or prevent the course of infection. After the disease develops, the patient is treated with anti-viral

drugs. In severe course of the disease, especially in children who are not vaccinated, the disease is associated with secondary bacterial infections leading to the development of phlegmon (usually streptococcal or staphylococcal infections, pneumonia, myocarditis, etc.), and in rare cases it can even be aggravated by the development of necrotic fasciitis, or toxic shock [5]. After the passed infection, lifelong immunity is formed. The experience of using vaccination against chickenpox is more than 30 years. At present, it is found in many countries of the world (Austria, Belgium, Finland, Poland, etc.) vaccination against chickenpox is carried out among persons belonging to the risk group. USA, Canada, Germany etc. in other countries, such as the vaccination against chickenpox is carried out within the framework of the national calendar of vaccinations, in other words, mass. In the United States, a weakened live vaccine against chickenpox is available to the entire population. For this purpose, a combination vaccine against "*measles – mumps - rubella - chickenpox*" (*MMRCH*) is widely used among children, which provides effective protection, especially for patients suffering from immunodeficiency. It should be noted that such vaccination carried out within 3-5 days after infection can prevent or alleviate the course of the disease [8].

The purpose of the study. Investigation of the peculiarities of the course of *chickenpox* in children who are not vaccinated.

Materials and methods. The examinations were carried out on 22 sick children (14 boys, 8 girls) with no specific prevention. Of these: up to 1 Year - 2 (9.1%); 1-3 years - 16 (72.7%); 4-7 years - 3 (13.6%); 8-15 years-1 (4.5%). Patient-yin Diagnostics was based on epidemiological Anamnesis data and the character clinical picture of the disease (intoxication syndrome, exanthemes and catarrhal signs) (Table-1).

Table-1.

Sex		By ages					Total
Boys n=14	Girls n=8	0-1 n=2	1-3 n=16	4-7 n=3	8-15 n=1	n=22	
63,6%	36,4%	9,1%	72,7%	13,6 %	4,5%	100%	

Results of the study. As can be seen from the table, boys are more often ill with chickenpox, and children aged 1-3 years prevail among patients. With increasing age, the incidence of morbidity decreases to a minimum in older age groups. According to the law, the majority of patients fall on children's institutions with a high level of contact (69%). The greatest incidence rate falls on the winter-spring period (54 and 26%, respectively), and the majority of patients (74%) had direct contact with a patient with chickenpox. Depending on the level of intoxication syndrome, localization and nature of the rash, as well as the duration of the rash, mild form of the disease was determined in 8 (36.4%) children, moderate - severe in 12 (54.5%) and severe in 2 (9.1%) children (more often in school-age children). In mild forms, the duration of high fever in patients was 2 ± 2.1 days, in moderate forms - 3.5 ± 1.7 days, in severe forms - 5 ± 2.0 days, in all cases, the duration of rashes of polymorphic (papule-vesicle-peeling) was 5.4 ± 2.5 days. Damage to the mucous membrane of the oral cavity was observed in 10 (45.5%) patients, enlargement of the lymph nodes (more often the maxillary and neck) was observed in 5 (22.7%) patients. In children under 1 year of age, no complications were fixed, in school-aged children with 2 aggravated premorbid background, a secondary bacterial infection (broncho-pneumonia, pyoderma) and complications in the form of febrile seizures were recorded, in 1 child, transitory thrombocytopenia was detected. A general blood test showed a decrease in hemoglobin concentration in 3 (13.6%) patients, mild leukocytosis in 4 (18.1%) patients, and ESR acceleration in 7 (31.8%) patients. While the treatment measures carried out in mild forms are limited to the treatment of rash elements with 2% brilliant green, general strengthening and symptomatic therapy, patients with moderate and severe forms have been prescribed antiviral specific drugs (Acyclovir, Genferon-light) for 4-7 days. Antibacterial and infusion therapy was carried out in patients with recorded bacterial complications.

Closing. Thus, the analysis reaffirms that chickenpox disease occurs mostly in winter-spring and mostly in children aged 1-3 years. The fact that the disease takes an epidemic picture is often accompanied by bacterial complications of the skin and lower respiratory tract, and in most cases a flat dependence is established between such complications and an aggravated premorbid background. Immunodeficiency states, especially its generalized forms, pose a greater risk of unsatisfactory course of chickenpox. In recent years, the increase in the number of cases of chickenpox and its accompanying pathologies, especially in sick children suffering from immunodeficiency, are often accompanied by one or other complications, once again confirms how important it is to carry out active immunization against this infection. In recent years, such a wide spread of the

incidence of chickenpox and its concomitant pathologies, especially in children suffering from immunodeficiency, often accompanied by these and other complications, create a significant basis for the importance of active immunization against this infection.

References:

1. Voronin E.M. Modern epidemiological features of chickenpox and approaches to its prevention: Abstract. dis. ... candidate of medical Sciences. Moscow; 2012.// Воронин Е.М. Современные эпидемиологические особенности ветряной оспы и подходы к ее профилактике: Автореф. дис. ... канд. мед. наук. Москва; 2012.
2. Sergeeva I.V., Lipnyagova S.V., Bekert A.I., Levitsky S.V., Borisov A.G. modern features of the course of chickenpox // Modern problems of science and education.- 2015. № 5. URL: // Сергеева И.В., Липнягова С.В., Бекерт А.И., Левицкий С.В., Борисов А.Г. современные особенности течения ветряной оспы // Современные проблемы науки и образования.- 2015. № 5. URL: <https://science-education.=22220>
3. Yu. Lobzina. Chickenpox in children in modern conditions (epidemiology, clinic, diagnosis, therapy, prevention) : a medical manual for doctors / edited by N. Y.V. Lobzin. SPb., 2011. 80 p.// Лобзина Ю.Б. Ветряная оспа у детей в современных условиях (эпидемиология, клиника, диагностика, терапия, профилактика) : лечебное пособие для врачей / под ред. Ю.В. Лобзина. СПб., 2011. 80 с.
4. Balashov D.N. Vaccination against chickenpox of immunocompromised patients. Literature review. Questions of hematology, oncology and immunopathology. 2011; 6: 10 – 16.// Балашов Д.Н. Вакцинация против ветряной оспы иммунокомпрометированных пациентов. Обзор литературы. Вопросы гематологии, онкологии и иммунопатологии. 2011; 6: 10 – 16.
5. Krasnova E.I., Gaints O.V., Gavrilova N.I., Kuimova I.V., Vasyunin A.V. Hemorrhagic form of chickenpox in children and its outcomes based on their own observations, possibilities of prevention. The attending physician. 2012; 3: 65-68.//Краснова Е.И., Гайнц О.В., Гаврилова Н.И., Куимова И.В., Васюнин А.В. Геморрагическая форма ветряной оспы у детей и ее исходы по материалам собственных наблюдений, возможности профилактики. Лечащий врач. 2012; 3: 65–68.
6. Rummyantsev A.G. Effectiveness and safety of vaccination against chickenpox in children. Zaporozhye Medical Journal-2011.-Vol.4, p.11-16 Румянцев А.Г. Эффективность и безопасность вакцинации против ветряной оспы у детей. Запорожский медицинский журнал-2011.-Т.4,с.11-16

7. Marin M, Marti M, Kambhampati A, Jeram SM, Seward JF. Global varicella vaccine effectiveness: a metaanalysis. *Pediatrics*. 2016;137(3):e20153741. doi: 10.1542/peds.2015-3741

8. Seward J.F., Watson B.M., Peterson C.L., Mascola L., Pelosi J.W., Zhan J.X. et al. Varicella disease after introduction of varicella vaccine in the

United States, 1995 – 2000. *JAMA*. 2002; 287: 606 – 611.

9. Communicable Diseases Network Australia. Varicella zoster (shingles), Varicella zoster infection (not elsewhere classified). Australian Government Department of Health; 2018